

Directed Routing: How Boundary-spanners Shape the Trajectory of Cross-Sector Knowledge Diffusion

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Abstract

How do boundary-spanning individuals shape the diffusion of scientific knowledge? Using bibliometric data to trace citation trajectories, we explore their impact along two dimensions. First, boundary-spanner-led research reaches significantly more distinct institutional sectors than single-sector research. Second, this diffusion operates as a directed conduit: boundary-spanners channel knowledge toward the specific external sectors in which they are embedded. For instance, a university-hospital boundary-spanner with only university-based co-authors produces research cited by hospital researchers at roughly twice the baseline rate (+12.5 percentage points). This directed routing pattern holds across all examined sector combinations (+8 to +14 percentage points). These findings reveal that multi-sector academic careers serve a specific systemic function. Rather than simply broadcasting knowledge to wider audiences, boundary-spanners act as directed pipelines, routing scientific knowledge toward practice-oriented sectors it would otherwise rarely reach.

Keywords: boundary-spanners, cross-sector knowledge diffusion, directed routing, citation analysis

1. Introduction

A companion study¹ establishes that boundary-spanners (researchers simultaneously affiliated with multiple sectors) are positively associated with higher citation impact (Authors, 2026). This finding is independently corroborated in Tong (2025, Chapter 6). But the value of multi-sector careers extends beyond citation volume. Because these individuals occupy a "third space of hybridity" and act as bridging agents between distinct organizational domains (Aldrich & Herker, 1977; Bednarek et al., 2018; Lam, 2018; Tushman & Scanlan, 1981; Williams, 2002), it is reasonable to infer that boundary-spanners also shape the direction of knowledge flows. They channel research toward sectors that can translate it into practice. Assessing their systemic contribution to innovation ecosystems therefore requires shifting focus from citation counts to the actual trajectory of knowledge diffusion.

Existing literature on cross-sector collaboration has concentrated on the citation impact of research output (Abramo et al., 2009; Bloch et al., 2019; Lebeau et al., 2008; Nast et al., 2025; Paswan et al., 2022). Far less attention has been paid to the pathways through which knowledge moves across institutional boundaries. It remains unclear how knowledge generated by individual boundary-spanners reaches other sectors and which sectors it ultimately penetrates. Yet, this empirical question is fundamental to understanding what boundary-spanners actually

¹ Author (2026) refers to a companion manuscript currently under double-blind peer review. That study empirically establishes the positive relationship between individual boundary-spanning roles and overall citation impact, serving as the theoretical point of departure for the diffusion analysis conducted in this paper.

contribute. E.g., a paper cited 100 times entirely within academia and one cited 100 times by a mix of academics, clinicians, and policy analysts perform identically on standard bibliometric indicators. Their roles in cross-sector knowledge translation, however, differ fundamentally. This study addresses this gap by asking whether and how boundary-spanners extend research transfer across sectors. Our central finding is that boundary-spanners contribute to knowledge diffusion not only by reaching more sectors, but by directing knowledge toward the specific sectors in which they are personally embedded. Compared to papers produced solely within the university sector, research led by university-hospital boundary-spanners diffuses more frequently to hospitals, being cited by hospital-affiliated researchers at approximately twice the field baseline rate. Boundary-spanners do not simply cast a wider net; they build directed bridges.

2. Data and methods

2.1 Data and sample

We utilize the Web of Science Core Collection (accessed via the Chinese Academy of Sciences' WoS-BP database), selecting all articles and reviews published in 2018, with citing data collected through 2020, yielding a two-year citation window. Institutional affiliations are mapped to five sector types using a custom classification database: Universities (U), Research Institutes (R), Industry (I), Hospitals (H), and Government (G). This database integrates foundational data from the Research Organization Registry (ROR)² and references the institutional classification scheme of Clarivate's InCites³. Building upon this combined baseline, our classification process further refines the data through keyword-based matching and rigorous manual verification, restricted to institutions publishing at least 100 papers per year.

2.2 Identifying boundary-spanners and paper classification

We operationalize boundary-spanning from bibliometric data by exploiting affiliation information recorded in Web of Science publication records. Each author's institutional affiliations are mapped to sector types. An author is classified as a boundary-spanning individual if their affiliations on a given paper span two or more different sector types. A paper is classified as "boundary-spanner-led" if at least one of its first or corresponding authors holds simultaneous affiliations in multiple sectors. Figure 1 illustrates the process.

² <https://ror.org/>

³ <https://incites.zendesk.com/hc/en-gb/articles/25088794628369-Institutions>

Figure 1: Illustration of the boundary-spanners identification procedure

For each focal paper, we identify all citing papers and extract the sectoral affiliations of their authors. Among citing-paper institutions, 66.0% are successfully matched to our classification database; unmatched institutions are excluded. To ensure meaningful citation profiles, we restrict the analysis to papers with at least 10 citations, yielding a final analytical sample of 175,152 papers. The main analysis compares two groups⁴:

- **Group A** (Single-sector, N = 155,822) contains papers whose authors are all affiliated with a single sector type.
- **Group B** (Boundary-spanner-led, N = 19,330) contains papers where at least one first or corresponding author simultaneously holds affiliations in two or more sector types.

2.3 Measuring cross-sector diffusion

We construct three measures that capture progressively deeper aspects of diffusion structure.

- **Citing sector count.** It is the number of distinct sector types represented among citing papers' authors (range: 1–5). This measures whether a paper's influence reaches a broad sectoral audience.
- **Shannon entropy of citing sectors (H_{sector}).** $H_{sector} = -\sum_{s=1}^S p_{s,i} \ln(p_{s,i})$, where $p_{s,i}$ is the proportion of sector type s among citing-author affiliations for paper i , and S represents the total number of possible sector types. While the sector count measures how many sectors are reached, entropy captures how evenly citations distribute across them. A paper cited by three sectors but with 95% of citations from universities has lower entropy than one with a more balanced 30%–30%–40% split.
- **Directed citation share measures.** For Group B papers where the boundary-spanner's "extra" sector can be cleanly identified (a sector to which the boundary-spanners personally belongs but which is absent from the co-author list), the share of citations originating from that sector. The comparison benchmark is the average citation share from the same sector for A-group papers in the same field.

⁴ Two additional groups: team-based cross-sector papers where no individual author personally spans sectors (N = 23,607) and papers involving non-led multi-sector authors (N = 12,123), are documented but excluded from the main baseline comparison to ensure a clean separation of mechanisms.

2.4 Empirical strategy

To isolate structural differences in diffusion patterns, we estimate the following ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model:

$$Y_{p,f} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{BoundarySpanner}_p + \gamma' \mathbf{X}_p + \delta_f + \varepsilon_{p,f}$$

where $Y_{p,f}$ represents the dependent variables capturing the cross-sector diffusion of paper p in field f . We estimate this model separately for two distinct outcomes: the citing sector count (to measure diffusion breadth) and the Shannon entropy of citing sectors (to measure diffusion structure). BoundarySpanner_p is a binary indicator equal to 1 for Group B papers and 0 for Group A papers (the reference category). \mathbf{X}_p is a set of paper-level controls, including team size, number of institutions, number of countries, and the natural logarithm of total citations. δ_f represents field fixed effects, and $\varepsilon_{p,f}$ is the error term.

The citation count control within \mathbf{X}_p is critical. Because more-cited papers mathematically reach more sectors, controlling for citation volume allows us to isolate structural differences in diffusion patterns at equal levels of impact. We estimate all models using robust standard errors (HC1) to account for heteroskedasticity.

3. Results

3.1 Broader reach and more balanced diffusion

Table 1: Descriptive statistics by paper group

	Group A (N = 155,822)	Group B (Boundary-spanner-led, N = 19,330)
Mean citing sector count	2.46	2.95
Mean total citations	20.0	22.6
Mean team size (N_{author})	4.8	8.0
Mean institutions (N_{ins})	1.7	3.7

As Table 1 shows, boundary-spanner-led papers reach substantially more sectors than single-sector papers. The raw mean for Group B (2.95 sectors) clearly exceeds that of Group A (2.46 sectors). While Group B papers also exhibit larger average team sizes and more institutional affiliations, Table 2 demonstrates that this diffusion advantage remains highly significant even after strictly controlling for these covariates.

Table 2: Diffusion breadth and structure — regression results

Variable	Citing sector count	Shannon entropy (H_{sector})
Group B (Boundary-spanner-led, ref: Group A)	0.240*** (0.007)	0.152*** (0.003)
$\ln(\text{Total citations})$	0.725*** (0.004)	0.066*** (0.001)
Controls + Field FE	Yes	Yes
Observations	175,152	175,152
R^2	0.284	0.243

Note: OLS regression. Robust standard errors (HCl) in parentheses. Controls include N_author , N_ins , N_cnt . * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

The results in Table 2 reveal a clear structural advantage for boundary-spanner-led papers. In terms of diffusion breadth, boundary-spanner-led papers reach approximately 0.24 more sector types than single-sector papers, conditional on citation volume and research field. More importantly, this expanded reach is accompanied by a fundamental shift in diffusion structure. Rather than exhibiting a highly concentrated citation profile dominated by a single sector (typically academia), boundary-spanner-led papers achieve significantly higher Shannon entropy (+0.152, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that their research achieves a structurally balanced diffusion profile, with citations distributed more evenly across the institutional boundaries they bridge.

3.2 Directed routing (University+X vs. University-only baseline): knowledge flows toward the boundary-spanner's connected sector

Having established that boundary-spanner-led papers achieve a broader and more balanced diffusion structure, we next investigate the specific trajectories of these citations. Specifically, we examine whether citations from boundary-spanner-led papers are systematically directed toward the external sector to which the boundary-spanners is personally connected. We restrict the analysis to Group B papers where the boundary-spanner's extra sector can be cleanly identified (i.e., a sector the boundary-spanners personally belongs to, but which is absent from the co-author list). We focus specifically on "University+X" combinations to capture the fundamental trajectory of knowledge transitioning from scientific production to practical application. Because universities serve as the primary locus of knowledge production, observing how citations flow from university-based toward practice-oriented external sectors provides an ideal context for isolating the directed routing effect. Using these University+X combinations from Group B against University-only papers from Group A as the comparison benchmark, this yields 5,213 papers. For each, we compare the citation share from the extra sector against the baseline for Group A papers in the same field.

Figure 2: Directed routing effect (University+X vs. University-only baseline): citation share

from the boundary-spanner's connected sector

Regarding to the University+X vs. University-only sample, Figure 2 presents the directed routing results. Each pair of bars compares Group B papers (whose co-authors are all university-based, but whose first or corresponding author holds an additional affiliation in the indicated sector) against Group A baseline papers in the same field. Differences range from +8.6 to +14.1 percentage points (all $p < 0.01$).

The pattern is consistent, large, and directional across all sector combinations. A university–research institute boundary-spanner whose co-authors are all university-based produces research cited by research institute authors at a rate of 27.2%, more than double the 13.1% baseline for all-university papers in the same field. University–hospital boundary-spanners exhibit a nearly identical effect, drawing 27.3% of citations from hospitals compared to a 14.8% baseline. For government affiliations, the ratio approaches four-fold (13.0% vs. 3.6%). For industry, the ratio is nearly thirty-fold (8.9% vs. 0.3%), though the small sample ($N = 31$) limits the robustness of this finding.

These pronounced effects point directly to the role of the boundary-spanning individual. By construction, the co-author networks of Group A and Group B papers in this analysis are functionally identical, as both consist entirely of university-based teams. The singular difference is the lead author's additional personal affiliation in an external sector. Consequently, this individual's cross-sector embedding is strongly associated with the dramatic divergence from the academic baseline. Consistent with established literature on their bridging roles (Tushman & Scanlan, 1981; Williams, 2002; Yegros-Yegros et al., 2021), the boundary-spanner's presence facilitates the breaking of boundaries. Crucially, this boundary-crossing diffusion is not diffuse or random, but systematically aligns with the directed routing of knowledge toward the connected sector.

The directed routing results provide crucial context for the entropy findings in Section 3.1. Mathematically, a higher Shannon entropy indicates that citations are less concentrated within the academic baseline. However, entropy alone does not reveal how this balance is achieved, i.e., whether knowledge is scattered indiscriminately across all non-academic sectors, or channeled into specific domains. The results in Figure 2 demonstrate that this shift in distribution is highly targeted. Boundary-spanners do not simply broadcast knowledge in all directions to achieve higher entropy; rather, the data indicate that this broader diffusion is, at least in part, explained by a targeted flow of knowledge toward the specific sectors in which the authors are embedded. They function as directed pipelines rather than omnidirectional broadcasters.

4. Discussion and conclusion

4.1 Not only wider nets, but also directed bridges

The main contribution of this study is identifying the mechanism through which boundary-spanning individuals shape knowledge diffusion. They not only extend the reach of research to more sectors, but also precisely route knowledge toward the specific sector in which they are personally embedded.

This distinction reframes what boundary-spanners contribute to innovation ecosystems. While a companion study (Author, 2026) established their positive effect on overall citation impact, the present study reveals an equally distinctive role in knowledge diffusion: broader reach

combined with directed routing. A researcher simultaneously embedded in a university and a hospital does not merely produce better-cited work. They produce research that finds its way to hospital-based audiences at rates that team composition alone cannot achieve, even when the co-author list contains no other hospital-based collaborators.

This directed routing mechanism is likely twofold. First, the boundary-spanner's cross-sector embedding shapes the research itself (including its problem selection, framing, and methodology) in ways that make it highly legible and relevant to practitioners in the connected sector. Second, the boundary-spanner's personal network in that sector provides a visibility channel: researchers there are more likely to encounter the work through professional contacts, shared institutional platforms, or sector-specific venues. This directed diffusion likely results from a combination of content and network channels, though isolating their respective effects remains an important task for future research.

4.2 Policy implications

The finding that boundary-spanning individuals act as directed bridges offers concrete guidance for science policy and institutional governance. Our empirical results support the promotion of multi-sector embedding as an effective model for facilitating the transition of knowledge from academic production to practical application. Individual researchers operating in these dual roles serve as structural conduits, channeling knowledge directly to practitioners through the research process itself.

This insight carries implications for funding strategy. Because the directed routing mechanism suggests that the sectoral combination of the individual dictates the destination of the knowledge, future scientific policy could benefit from establishing dedicated funding programs specifically designed for boundary-spanning roles. To promote evidence-based policymaking, for instance, university-government dual appointments merit targeted structural support to build reliable, directed knowledge channels.

Finally, these results offer a new perspective on the institutional governance of multi-sector careers. As detailed in Author (2026), universities often restrict external engagements out of concern for academic time commitment. Our diffusion analysis adds a structural dimension to this debate. It suggests that limiting a boundary-spanner's external affiliation goes beyond merely reclaiming working hours; it inadvertently shuts down a directed route for knowledge dissemination. Institutions may benefit from governance models that balance the need for faculty focus with the structural advantages of cross-sector knowledge routing

4.3 Limitations and work in progress

Several limitations should be acknowledged. Citation-based diffusion proxies knowledge attention, not knowledge use. The two-year citation window captures early diffusion patterns but may miss longer-term compositional shifts. The directed diffusion analysis is restricted to Group B papers with identifiable extra sectors (N=5,213), and industry boundary-spanners are underrepresented (N=31). Additionally, our current institutional matching process excludes organizations that fall below the publication threshold. While this captures 66.0% of citing affiliations, it may undercount knowledge diffusion to highly specialized or smaller practice-oriented entities. Furthermore, the current analysis is associational. Boundary-spanners may select into topics that inherently attract cross-sector audiences, though field fixed effects partially mitigate this concern. Causal identification, e.g., policy-based natural experiments, remains a priority for future work.

As a study in progress, we are expanding our classification database to incorporate a more comprehensive coverage of institutions, which will refine our baseline diffusion metrics. We are also currently examining whether team-based cross-sector papers (which have been excluded in current analysis) exhibit comparable directional diffusion patterns. This will allow us to compare the individual embedding mechanism against network-based explanations and more precisely attribute the directed routing effect. Additionally, we are actively extending our analysis to disentangle the twofold mechanism proposed earlier. Specifically, we aim to empirically determine whether this boundary-crossing knowledge diffusion is primarily driven by substantive adaptations in research content, the mobilization of the boundary-spanner's personal network resources, or a combination of both.

Open science practices

The raw bibliometric data underlying our analysis were sourced from the Web of Science Core Collection. Due to the licensing agreements of Clarivate, we are not legally permitted to publicly share the raw publication and citation records. However, researchers can replicate our data collection process detailed in the methodology section via their own institutional WoS subscriptions.

To ensure the reproducibility of our findings, we are committed to making our analytical process openly available. The institution-sector classification dictionary used to map affiliations to sector types, alongside the Python source code utilized for data cleaning, entropy calculations, and statistical modeling, have been prepared for open access. To maintain the integrity of the current double-blind peer review process, these materials are temporarily withheld. They will be deposited in a public repository.

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Author contributions

Sichao Tong: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Liyang Yang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision

Competing interests

Authors have no competing interests.

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